

MANUFACTURING OF PREDOMINANTLY BIO-BASED COMPOSITE PROFILES WITH PULTRUSION

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ABSTRACT

The composite industry is constantly investigating new materials and manufacturing technologies with the goal of increasing the market share in typical applications for materials such as steel, aluminium or wood. Continuous fibre reinforced polymer composites manufactured by pultrusion are expected to play an important role in the substitution of profiles, boards and tubes made of steel, aluminium and wood in applications demanding a high mechanical performance in the longitudinal orientation. For the pultrusion process, a holistic approach by developing suitable fibre-matrix combinations together with the processing technology is essential to meet customer requirements regarding cost and production efficiency.

During the last years, composites based on renewable sources gained huge interest in the wake of a globally increased awareness on sustainability topics regarding manufacturing processes and applications of fibre reinforced polymeric materials.

In this study, a unique combination of cellulose regenerated fibres and a novel bio-based polyurethane (PU) matrix material approaching a bio-based content of approximately 90 % was investigated.

The pultrusion process using bio-based composites was developed applying a two-step methodology. Firstly, processing parameters and resin formulations of the bio-based polyurethane were optimized in a standard pultrusion process with glass as fibre material. Subsequently, the processing of cellulose regenerated fibres (CRF) was investigated in combination with the optimized resin formulations. The mechanical properties of the produced pultruded profiles were tested and benchmarked with profiles produced with a standard matrix-fibre combination. The high profile quality and mechanical properties of the produced profiles with a bio-based content of up to 90% demonstrate clearly the technical and commercial feasibility of producing high performance bio-based FRP profiles for use in applications with a need for high unidirectional strength and excellent weathering and mechanical stability.

1 INTRODUCTION

The pultrusion process is an established manufacturing method for obtaining high quality fibre reinforced plastic (FRP) profiles with constantly high mechanical properties and offers additional advantages such as high productivity and comparatively low investment costs. Pultruded composite profiles are composed of reinforcing fibres (e.g. glass, carbon or aramid) - individually or in combination - enclosed in a polymer matrix (e.g. polyester, vinyl ester, epoxy or phenolic).

The pultrusion process is thus a high value added process leading to high performance products at low production and energy costs. All these aspects have led to an increasing use in a broad variation of applications. [1] The field of application of pultrudates range from medical and dental [2-4], infrastructure and construction [5, 6] to the transport and automotive sectors [7]. In addition to the lightweight construction potential of pultrusion profiles, the general advantages of FRP such as high corrosion resistance, good electrical and thermal insulation properties and in case of aliphatic PU also high weathering resistance are decisive reasons for their use [1, 5, 11]. The properties of a pultrudate depend not only on the raw materials (fibres and matrix) composition but also strongly on the processing history.

The term pultrusion refers to the process principle: reinforcing fibres impregnated with a matrix resin are pulled through a heated die. In the die, the matrix material hardens through polymerization and the composite is created in one step in the desired shape. The process for the production of composite profiles with a constant cross-section was developed by W. B. Goldsworthy [8] in the United States at the end of the 1950s. Pultrusion technology currently accounts for about five percent of glass fibre reinforced plastic composite (GRP) production in Europe. In 2018 the total production of GRP pultrudates amounted to around 55 kt comprising a growth of ten percent compared to 2015. [9]

The use of materials on a renewable basis is becoming a pressing issue worldwide. Accordingly, composites on a renewable basis are nowadays a focus of research. [10] Therefore, in this study a bio-based PU system was chosen which is known for its good fire, smoke and droplet classification (FSD) in combination with a high glass transition temperature (T_g) and good flex fatigue properties [11, 12].

2 DEFINING THE PULTRUSION PROCESSING CONDITIONS

2.1 PULTRUSION PROCESS AND EQUIPMENT

The intended component parts/profiles and the required load cases determine the choice of the fibre package and the selection of the matrix system. Accordingly, the design of the tool and impregnation system as well as the process control and production set-up was customised. For the production of high-performance composite profiles using the pultrusion process it is necessary to achieve a uniform impregnation of uniaxial and multiaxial textile semi-finished products with the matrix material. There are various open and closed process variants for this purpose known [13]. Fig. 1 schematically shows the pultrusion process with open bath impregnation. The principal steps of the process are represented: (1) roving and textile providing with preforming, (2) impregnation (process variant dip bath), (3) die for curing, (4) take-off unit and packaging.

Figure 1: Basic elements of a pultrusion line

2.2 METHODOLOGY

The development took place in a two-step procedure. The first step addressed the processing of the new bio-based PU system in the pultrusion process and in the second step the introduction of a cellulose regenerated fibres was investigated. Due to an ongoing publicly funded project and a joined non-disclosure agreement (NDA) among participating project partners, no details about the chemical composition of the bio-based PU system can be disclosed at this time. Four variations of the resin formulations investigated are specified with the characters A to D. A highly viscous aliphatic PU resin system, newly established by Covestro, was taken as the baseline for development (formulation A). After setting the baseline with formulation A, three different resin formulations (B, C, D) were tested. For that purpose, formulation A was mixed with more than 20 % of different bio-based diluents. The resin variations further differ in the quantity of accelerators. Glass fibres (GF) were selected as the reinforcement material during the first investigation stage due to their known suitability for the pultrusion process and to keep this variable constant.

The fibres were impregnated in an injection and impregnation chamber (ii-chamber) with conical geometry (1) and then pulled through a heated die of 1000 mm length and 4 tempering zones (2) (see Figure 2). A composite profile of cross section 120 x 4 mm² and 67% fibre volume fraction (FVF) was thus continuously pulled out of the die (3). The resin was injected by means of a pressure pot with three injection nozzles located at the top and bottom sides of the ii-chamber (4). The liquid pressure in the ii-chamber was measured by a pressure transducer (5) to get feedback on the process status.

Figure 2: Pultrusion setup

Firstly, the processing conditions were optimised, using the conventional parameters for the commercial aliphatic petro-based system (Desmocomp[®] by Covestro) as reference. Accordingly, a Desmocomp-GF composite was used as a benchmark for the composites with the new resin formulations. All trials were performed at three different pulling speeds (0.3, 0.5 and 0.8 m/min), to evaluate the influence of the line speed on the composite properties. Contrary to the Desmocomp-GF composites, where a significant increase in mechanical properties was observed with increasing pulling speed, the characteristic properties of the composites with the resin formulations B-D decrease with increasing pulling speed.

After identifying the processing parameters, cellulose regenerated fibres (CRFs) were processed within the second development stage. Preliminary studies show that CRFs contain up to 8% moisture. The water acts as a blowing agent creating bubbles in the matrix via CO₂ formation, when processed with Isocyanates at higher temperatures. Therefore, an inline infrared fibre-drying passage (1) was implemented into the pultrusion line, upstream of the impregnation unit (see Figure 3). The fibres were pulled through guide plates (2) and then impregnated in a dip bath (3). Consecutively the wetted fibres were pulled out of the bath, passed through a squeeze out plate (4) and then through a pultrusion die of a cross section of 30 x 4 mm² (5). The FVF of 67 % was kept constant. Table 1 gives an overview of the fibres, resin formulations and impregnation methods used in both development steps.

Trial	Resin	Fibre	Impregnation-Method
Ref.	Desmocomp [®]	GF	conical ii-chamber
A	A	GF	conical ii-chamber
B	B	GF	conical ii-chamber
C	C	GF	conical ii-chamber
D	D	GF	conical ii-chamber
Ref_CRF	C	CRF	dip bath
C_CRF	C	CRF	dip bath

Table 1: Design of Experiments: used fibres, resin and impregnation method

The resulting – predominantly bio-based – composite (6) was then benchmarked against the conventional GF composite in terms of its mechanical and thermochemical behaviour. Interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) and 3-point flexural strength were used to determine the mechanical properties of the material. Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA) was used to determine the glass transition temperature (T_g).

Figure 3: Laboratory setup (left) and schematic representation of the assembly (right)

3 RESULTS, EVALUATION AND DISCUSSION

The initial viscosity of resin formulation A was approx. 25 Pa·s, which led to incomplete and non-uniform impregnation. Consequently, a stable pultrusion process could not be achieved. Subsequently, the starting formulation A was modified to achieve a lower viscosity by mixing a reactive thinner. Three additional different resin formulations were used: B (viscosity ~5 Pa·s), C (viscosity ~2 Pa·s) and D (viscosity ~2 Pa·s). Already with formulation B it was possible to manufacture composites at a line speed of 0.3 m/min and 0.5 m/min. At 0.8 m/min an insufficient wetting of the fibres and numerous furrows and resin pellets occurred on the surface of the composite. The resulting material was therefore not further analysed. All other composites were analysed with the above described testing program.

The composites made with the resin formulations C and D showed the best results of all formulations regarding bending stress. If the values of the bending stress are compared for a line speed of 0.3 m/min in Figure 4, an increase for the resin formulations B - D results against the petro-based reference composite (Ref) can be seen. For the composites out of formulation B the figure is 16 % above the reference value, while for the C and D composites the bending stress is higher by more than 30 %.

Figure 4: Bending stress for different resin formulation and pulling speeds

Comparing the interlaminar shear strength (see Figure 5), a value of 55 MPa was determined for the petro-based reference system at pulling speeds 0.3 and 0.5 m/min. This value was insensitive to speed variation. With the bio-based modified resin formulations B – D, as well as in the bending stress, a decrease of the characteristic values was observed for the pulling speed increase. The values of the formulation C were at a pulling speed 0.3 m/min more than 20 % above the reference value, while those of the resin system D were 16 % higher. It is noticeable that the values for resin C remain almost constant over the different pulling speeds, while for formulation D there was a decrease in interlaminar shear strength of 12% between the minimum and maximum pulling speeds.

Figure 5: Interlaminar shear strength for different resin formulation and pulling speeds

The Tg of the composites based on formulations C and D are 20 % higher than the petro-based reference system. Formulation D shows a strong correlation between line speed and Tg. A composite processed with a higher pulling speed has a significantly lower Tg, see Figure 6. The effect of the line speed influence on the Tg of formulation C, with a change of 5 % between the minimum and maximum speed, was significantly lower than the 10 % change of formulation D.

Figure 6: Glass transition temperature (Tg) for different resin formulation and pulling speeds

The investigations suggested that lower viscosities were more suitable for the pultrusion process. Important factors for stable processing are the sufficient and uniform impregnation of the fibres with resin; a low and constant pulling force; and achieving a smooth and flat composite surface. These results were also reflected in the mechanical properties of the composites. The interlaminar shear strength and bending modulus of the composite increased with decreasing viscosity.

After a comparison and summary of the results obtained, the resin formulation C was defined for the second development stage. On this basis, the cellulose regenerated fibres were processed into composites using the modified test setup presented here. The pultrusion process ran stable and with low pulling force. The composites show a good surface quality and a steady impregnation, see Fig. 7.

Figure 7: CRF-Composite-Profiles

The cellulose regenerated fibre was processed with the petro-based reference system (Ref_CRF) and with the resin formulation C_CRF at a pulling speed of 0.3 m/min and 0.5 m/min. The material properties were also determined by three-point bending and ILSS testing. The characteristic values of the bending stress determined for the C-composites were significantly higher than those of the reference system, see Fig. 8.

Figure 8: Bending stress for different resin formulation (Desmocomp, C) and pulling speeds with CRF

When comparing the ILSS data of the reference system with the C-Composite, an increase of 27 % was observed at a pulling speed of 0.3 m/min. The decrease in the ILSS figures by increasing the pulling speed from 0.3 m/min to 0.5 m/min is greater for the reference system than for the C-composites, see Fig. 9.

Figure 9: Interlaminar shear strength for different resin formulation (Desmocomp, C) and pulling speeds with CRF

The achieved characteristic values of development stage 1 - where glass fibres were used - differ significantly from the values achieved development stage 2 - where bio-based CRFs were used. Evidently, the difference is due to the different fibre properties. The glass fibres have a modulus of elasticity of 72 GPa, the CRFs have a modulus of elasticity of 20 GPa. Further reasons for the difference in the mechanical performance could be attributed to different fibre-sizing-matrix interactions.

This work demonstrates the possibility of producing predominantly bio-based composites by pultrusion. Future work in the development of high-performance bio-based composites could include the use of bio-based carbon fibres.

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